

TEACHING METHODS

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ANNOTATION: The aim of this article giving information about suggestopedia which is considered one of the most modern teaching methods. Advantages and disadvantages as well as history of this method is also will be defined.

KEY WORDS: suggestopedia, learning process, vocabularly, teaching method

Education needs some new methods in order to help in the learning process. The learning process requires active involvement from the students that results from using appropriate teaching strategies. Firstly, what is teaching method. A teaching method comprises the principles and methods used by teachers to enable student learning. These strategies are determined partly on subject matter to be taught and partly by the nature of the learner. For a particular teaching method to be in relation with the characteristic of the learner and type of learning it is supposed to bring about. Suggestions are there to design and selection of teaching method must take into account not only the nature of the subject matter but also how students learn.[P. Westwood]. There are a large number of productive and effective teaching methods in learning process. Each of have its characteristics and feature that consists of objectives, environments and learning needs.

Suggestopedia is one of the most modern and best methods of teaching foreign languages. Suggestopedia, a portmanteau of “suggestion” and “pedagogy” is a teaching method used to learn a foreign languages and it is also known desuggestopedia. [Richards, J.C] This method is a method which foxuses on how to deal with the relationship between mental potential and learning efficacy and it uses music, a comfortable and relaxing environment. The level of memorization in learning through suggestopedia would be accelerated by up to 25times over than in conventional learning methods. Suggestopedia makes use of dialogs, situations, and translation to present and practice language, and in particular, makes the use of music, visual images, and relaxation exercises to make learning more comfortable and effective [Richard J.C] It is a method of teaching a foreign language in which students learn quickly by being made to

feel relaxed, interested, and positive [Hornby. 2005]. From this two definitions, it is clear that suggestopedia uses techniques to make students feel relaxed, comfortable, interested in order to learn more quickly.

Dr. Lozanov is a Bulgarian psychiatrist, psychotherapist, brain physiologist and educator. He has a passion for understanding how human beings learn. This led him to travel around the world to examine examples of super memory and learning achievements. Dr. Lozanov and his colleague, Dr. Evelyn Gateva, first applied the new methodology to teach foreign languages, with astounding results. The result was that students not only had fun, but that they also learn faster than with traditional teaching methods. Teachers begin to apply suggestion, relaxation and music to the learning process. While Lozanov was developing his methodology in Bulgaria, some cognitive scientists and educators in America were also taking great steps in understanding how the brain learns. For example, Harvard professor, Howard Gardner, developed the theory of Multiple Intelligence, and Dr. Antonio Damasio demonstrated how critical emotions influence learning. [Rivera, M.T]

Lozanov believes that learners may have been using only 5 to 10 percent of mental health capacity, and that the brain could process and retain much more material if given optimal conditions for learning. Based on psychological research, Lozanov began to develop a language learning method focusing on "desuggestion" of the limitations learners think they have, and providing the sort of relaxed state of mind that would facilitate the retention of material to its maximum potential. [Rustipa. K]

However, there exist both negative and positive sites of using suggestopedia in learning process. For example, in a research which carried out by Ostrander and Schroeder, it is said that baroque music created the kind of relaxed states of mind for maximum retention of material.

Advantages:

- *students can lower their affective filter
- *classes are held in ordinary rooms with comfortable chairs, a practice that may also help them relax
- *Authority concept
- *Students remember best and are most influenced by information coming from an authoritative source, teachers.
- *Double-planed theory: It refers to the learning from two aspects. They are the conscious aspect and the subconscious one. Students can acquire the aim of

teaching instruction from both direct institution and environment in which the teaching takes place.

*peripheral learning : suggestopedia encourages the students to apply language more independently, takes more personal responsibility for their own learning and get more confidence. Peripheral information can also help encourage students to be more experimental, and look to sources other than the teacher for language input.

Disadvantages:

*Environment limitation: most schools in developing countries have large classes. Each class consists of 30 to 40 students. There should be 12 students in a class.

*The use of hypnosis: some people say that suggestopedia uses a hypnosis, so it has had deep effects for human beings. Lozanov strongly denied about it.

*Infantilization learning: suggestopedia a class is conditioned to be child-like situation. There are some students who do not like to be treated like this as they think that they are mature.

In conclusion, suggestopedia is a method which focuses on how to deal with the relationship between mental potential and learning efficacy. This method was introduced by a Bulgarian psychologist and educator, George Lozanov in 1975. Suggestopedia has got its both merits and demerits in learning process.

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